

Research Article

SunChase: Automated Solar Energy Optimization System

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Abstract: As the Earth faces the impacts of global warming, harnessing solar energy through advanced tracking systems has become increasingly essential for sustainable energy production. Solar tracking systems are capable of efficient energy production as the solar panels are positioned perpendicular to the sun's rays. In this study, the design and construction of the solar tracker is based on Arduino Uno microcontroller as a main controller, which uses a Light Dependent Resistor (LDR) sensor as input to detect the sun's rays and direct a Micro Servo Motor (output) to adjust the position of the solar panel. The goal of the solar tracker is to receive the maximum amount of sun rays to increase the efficiency of the solar panel. By integrating tracking technology, efficiency and power output can be significantly enhanced, as well as reducing costs. In this research, the system is categorized as an active solar tracker using dual-axis system and the output results showed relatively consistent voltage readings throughout the day when the weather is clear with readings taken at 1-hour intervals.

Keywords: solar tracker; renewable energy; sustainable; UN SDG-7; UN SDG-13.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The combustion of fossil fuels, including coal, oil, and natural gas, for power generation results in the emission of significant quantities of greenhouse gases (GHG), such as carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane, which contribute to atmospheric warming (Filonchyk et al., 2024). The emission of CO₂ is a primary contributor to global warming and climate change (UN). Transitioning to renewable energy sources, such as solar energy, while endorsing UN Sustainable Development Goals 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and 13 (Climate Action) via sustainable energy initiatives, can mitigate carbon emissions and bolster global endeavours to address climate change (UN SDG).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This system is designed to automatically detect the highest light intensity and adjust its orientation accordingly using two micro servo motors. When a decrease in light intensity is detected, the system reorients itself to capture the maximum possible light. Controlled by an Arduino Uno microcontroller, the system operates efficiently, making it an ideal solution for residential and small industrial applications seeking to reduce long-term energy costs.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the system.

The system was implemented using an Arduino Uno microcontroller, four LDRs, two servo motors, an LED, and a voltmeter as depicted in the block diagram in Figure 1. The LDRs sense the amount of sunlight falling on them and the input of the system is divided into top, bottom, left, and right LDRs. The Arduino Uno microcontroller processes the input from the sensors and controls the output of the system. For east-west tracking, the analog values from the top and bottom LDRs are compared and the vertical servo moves in the direction where more light is received. For angular deflection of the solar panel, the analog values from the left and right LDRs are compared and the horizontal servo moves in the direction where more light is received. The output of the system includes two micro servo motors, an LED, and a voltmeter used to collect voltage in the solar panel. The project aims to maximize the production of electricity from sunlight compared to static solar panels. Final prototype is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Prototype of the system.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

When the system is begun to activate, the system is set to initial position. Then, it will read the input of the LDRs. The system will compare the light intensity of LDR sensor. The sensors send digital information about presence and absence of light intensity to the microcontroller. The condition starts with: if the LDRr senses the light is not equal than LDRI, the horizontal motor will rotate toward the higher sensor; east or west and if not, it will compare the light intensity of LDRt and LDRb. If LDRt is not equal to LDRb, the vertical motor will rotate toward the higher sensor; up or down. If there is no light that all LDR have sense, the motor will stop. The output demonstration can be seen via this link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hj3SDZZIUQY>.

3.1 Output voltage

The solar panel used in this research is a polycrystalline panel with features: 1W, 6V and 167mA. The output measurement of average voltage is 5.06V. This result showed relatively consistent voltage readings throughout the day when the weather is clear with readings taken at 1-hour intervals. This shows that the efficiency in absorbing solar energy using this system is as much as 84.33%.

4. CONCLUSION

This project successfully demonstrated an automatic solar tracking system that optimizes the alignment of solar panels with the sun's rays, significantly increasing the absorption of solar energy. By maximizing energy use, this system contributes to a more efficient and sustainable use of solar resources. Their cost-effectiveness and reliability make solar trackers particularly suitable for rural applications, where access to affordable renewable energy is often limited. These innovative solutions provide practical ways to increase energy accessibility and promote sustainable development in underserved areas.

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